

SOME ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING PROPER NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Barno Mukhtorova

teacher, Phd student, FerSU

Sobirova Kamola &

Yuldosheva Makhliyo

4th year students, FerSU

Abstract: this article covers the role of culture in presence and formation of proper nouns. The article deals with linguacultural peculiarities and translation problems of proper nouns. The linguacultural analysis of proper nouns demonstrates the relation of language with the history, spirituality and certainly, culture of nation. Taking into account of above-mentioned features, the problems of translation of proper nouns from one language into another was mentioned in this article.

Key words: language, culture, proper nouns, identification, linguacultural, linguistic units, transcription, transliteration, semantic modification, description, tracing and commenting.

Lexical transformations in translation occur between two different languages in order to preserve and transmit of meaning of words when they translate into another language. A model is a conventional representation of the translating process describing mental operations by which the source text or some part of it may be translated, irrespective of whether these operations are actually performed by the translator. It may describe the translating process either in a general form or by listing a number of specific operations (or transformations) through which the process can, in part, be realized. Translation models can be oriented either toward the situation reflected in the ST contents or toward the meaningful components of the ST contents. The existing models of the translating process are, in fact, based on the same assumptions which we considered in discussing the problem of

equivalence, namely, the situational (or referential) model is based on the identity of the situations described in the original text and in the translation, and the semantic-transformational model postulates the similarity of basic notions and nuclear structures in different languages. These postulates are supposed to explain the dynamic aspects of translation. In other words, it is presumed that the translator actually makes a mental travel from the original to some interlingual level of equivalence and then further on to the text of translation. In the situational model this intermediate level is extralinguistic. This is the first step of the process, i.e. the break-through to the situation. The second step is for the translator to describe this situation in the target language. Thus, the process goes from the text in one language through the extralinguistic situation to the text in another language. The translator first understands what the original is about and then says “the same things” in TL.

Types of words according to their formation. Words divide into three types due to their formation: simple word, compound word and couple word. The words which are formed only by a core - component are called simple words. For example: *она, она, сув, ақлли* and etc. Lexical transformations in turn are divided into three types: *transcription and transliteration, calque* and *types of lexical-semantic change*.

Transcription is primarily a reflection of the pronunciation of a language and is more "user-friendly".

Transcription is simpler and involves writing down the recording as text, to reflect the way the sounds are pronounced.

Transliteration on the other hand, is based on a scientific method supported by a coding system in which each letter has its equivalent in any other language.

Thus, while transcription makes it easier to pronounce foreign words, transliteration makes it possible to read sentences written in a foreign alphabet in general.

We can apply transcription methods to translate context free words in most cases. What are the context-free words? Some words, however, are less sensitive to the contextual influence than others. There are words with definite meanings, which are retained in most contexts, and are relatively context-free

They are:

- proper and geographical names;
- titles of magazines and newspapers;
- names of various firms, organizations; names of ships, aircraft;
- names of scientific terms;
- names of the months and days of the week,

EXAMPLES FOR TRANSCRIPTION

Proper and geographical names are transcribed with TL letters Proper names E.g.: Smith (СМИТ), Brown (Браун), John Fitzgerald Kennedy (ДЖОН Фитзгеральд Кеннеди); geographical names: Cleveland (Кливленд), Rhode Island (Роде Айленд), Downing Street (Даунинг Стрит), titles of periodicals: Life, Times (Лайф, Таймс) , Iowa (Айова), the names of firms: General Motors Corporation- (Дженерал Моторс Корпорэйшн)

EXAMPLES FOR TRANSCRIPTION

The names of ships, aircraft: Queen Elizabeth – “Квин Элизавет” (кема номи) Spitfire – “Спитфайе” (хаво кемаси); terms (technical, political, social, medical) Many Uzbek equivalents have been formed from the English terms by transcription or loan translations: computer (компьютер), electron (электрон); congressman (конгрессмен), impeachment (импичмент); resolution (резолуция), vaccine (вакцина), epidemic (эпидемия); names of the months: January (январь) and etc.

Calque. This transformation technique is often applied to translate compound terms or term phrases. In linguistics, a calque is actually a word or phrase borrowed from another language by literal, word-for-word translation. The term calque is borrowed from French and it derives from the verb calques which means to copy, to trace.

More specifically, we use the verb to calque when speaking about borrowing a word or phrase from another language while translating its components so as to create a new lexeme in the target language. For instance, skyscraper (осмонўпар).

Transparent local geographical names can be translated by calques: Rocky Mountains (Қояли тоғлар, скалистые горы), Saint Helena Island (Авлиё Елена Ороли), Golden Horn Bay (Олтин Шох Кўрфази), Far East (Узоқ Шарқ).

Half-calques can be used to translate toponyms with classifiers, such as river, lake, bridge: Waterloo Bridge (Ватерло Кўприги), Salt Lake City (Солт Лейк Сити: Тузли Кўл Шаҳри тарзида таржима қилинмайди), Tower Bridge (Тавер кўприги)

Transcription, or mixed methods are usually given in dictionaries. But, in most cases, especially historical and cultural names, rare geographical names, translation in the translation of new terms. The selection of the method is the responsibility of the translator and he is required to make an independent decision.

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